

Some Antimony(III) Dithiocarbamates

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RECENT reports¹⁻³ on bromobis- and iodobis dithiocarbamates of group VB metals prompted us to synthesise antimony monochlorobis-, dichloro- mono- and tris-dithiocarbamates by insertion as well as by metathetical reactions. Analytical and IR data are presented in support of their structure. The mode of decomposition has been examined through TGA experiments.

Experimental

The ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acid were prepared through reported method³. Antimony trichloride was obtained from Fischer Chemicals, U. S. A. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out at a heating rate of 5°/min using an instrument supplied by Fertilizer Corporation of India, Sindri (India). Infrared spectra were recorded in the region 4000-700 cm⁻¹ with Perkin Elmer model 337 and 700-250 cm⁻¹ using Perkin Elmer 521 in nujol mull between cesium iodide plates.

Antimony tris dithiocarbamates were synthesised through the insertion reaction :

where R₂ = aryl group

In a typical experiment 15 mmole of an amine was slowly added to a solution of antimony trichloride (5 mmole) and carbon disulfide (15 mmole) in 20-25 ml methanol at ~ -20° with constant stirring. After the addition was complete,

the mixture was further stirred for two hours and the separated solid product was filtered. It was dissolved in the minimum quantity of dichloromethane and the desired product precipitated by addition of pet ether (60-80°). It was recrystallised with the same solvents and dried under vacuum.

Antimony dichloro- mono-, monochlorobis-, and tris dithiocarbamates were prepared by the interaction of antimony trichloride with ammonium salt of dithiocarbamate in 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3 molar ratio respectively.

where R₂ = aryl group, n = 1, 2, or 3.

In a typical metathetical reaction 10 mmole of antimony(III) chloride and 10, 20, or 30 mmole of ammonium salt of dithiocarbamic acid were taken in 30 ml of methanol. The reaction mixture was stirred for two hours at room temperature and filtered, the solid product was extracted with dichloromethane. On distilling off the excess solvent and treating with petroleum ether yielded a pale yellow crystalline solid which was dried under vacuum and analysed.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data and the characteristic absorption frequencies of the newly synthesised dithiocarbamates are listed in Table 1. The compounds are yellow crystalline solids, stable at room temperature but decompose on heating at their melting points excepting those of pyrrolidine. They are insensitive to atmospheric oxygen and moisture and are insoluble in common organic solvents.

It has been reported earlier that doublets at

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND CHARACTERISTIC ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹)

Compound	Method	m.p. °C	Analysis % (obsd and (calcd.))			ν(C-N)	ν(C-S)	ν(Sb-S)
			Sb	C	H			
Sb(SCSN) ₃	a,b	205°	21.91 (21.72)	32.26 (32.41)	4.27 (4.31)	1510 s	1000 vs 948 vs	360 s
SbCl(SCSN) ₂	b	193°	27.80 (27.01)	26.64 (26.70)	3.53 (3.58)	1515 vs	1000 s 952 vs	370 vs
SbCl ₂ (SCSN)	b	135°	35.28 (35.92)	17.70 (17.72)	2.35 (2.38)	1517 vs	1000 vs 952 vs	372 vs
Sb(SCSNNC ₅ H ₉) ₃	a,b	130° d	14.26 (14.60)	47.49 (47.53)	4.68 (4.72)	1493 vs	1015 vs 990 m	390 s
SbCl(SCSNNC ₅ H ₉) ₂	b	88° d	19.81 (19.25)	41.77 (41.82)	4.03 (4.14)	1502 vs	1014 vs 995 m	390 s
SbCl ₂ (SCSNNC ₅ H ₉)	b	80° d	28.19 (28.31)	30.71 (30.72)	3.02 (3.04)	1505 vs	1015 vs 1000 vs	395 vs
Sb(SCSNO) ₃	a,b	225° d	19.97 (20.00)	29.58 (29.61)	4.15 (3.97)	1470 vs	1008 m 990 s	360 s
SbCl(SCSNO) ₂	b	202° d	25.18 (25.27)	24.81 (24.94)	3.43 (3.34)	1473 vs	1010 m 998 s	360 vs
SbCl ₂ (SCSNO)	b	180° d	34.21 (34.30)	16.88 (16.92)	2.30 (2.27)	1481 vs	1010 m 996 s	370 vs

